

ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP: EVALUATING SCHOOL HEADS' PERFORMANCE IN SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

This research undertaking is designed to evaluate the school heads' performance on the use of school-based management as a tool towards educational leadership. The study used a descriptive-correlational design to answer the research questions in which it determined the school management performance, the degree of receptiveness of teachers and stakeholders to the interventions introduced by their school heads, the extent to which the school interventions have contributed to school improvement, and teachers' performance. The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using the identified statistical treatment. The findings indicated that school heads demonstrated level II (maturing) performance in school-based management, encompassing leadership and governance, curriculum and instruction, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources. The results reveal that 58.3% (7 out of 12) of school heads were classified as "Receptive" to the introduced interventions. Interestingly, teachers developed learning modules, s manifested in the 3.00 rating of the school head and 2.77 by the teachers. The findings suggest that the school leaders have the potential to improve the quality of teaching and learning.

Keywords: Educational Leadership, Performance, School-Based Management, Descriptive-Correlational, Receptive, Department of Education

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine Department of Education (2020) also acknowledged the important position of school principals in the continuity of education amid Covid -19 crisis. It asserted obligation to give professional development to school principals. The school principals were trained to carry out the adoption of an array of learning delivery prototypes based on their preparedness, resources, and plans as this will result to quality learning amid the crisis. They were given an opportunity to be familiar with the range of learning prototypes they can employ depending on the capacity and situation of the community they are located. They were capacitated to lead the continuity of education in this time of pandemic.

Throughout history, all that have been required of successful principals is a strong grasp of management and political concepts. On the other hand, the expectations placed on schools in the 21st-century call for principals to possess diverse leadership qualities. In addition to strong instructional leadership skills, a principal's competence in this new educational period will demand knowledge and skills related to organizational culture and management. This need is because both of these areas are intertwined with one another (Consenza, 2015).

Because of the difficulty of implementing educational reform and the rapid pace at which society is transforming, it is now very necessary for schools to have capable principals serving in leadership roles. As heads of educational institutions, principals are tasked with the difficult task of enhancing both teaching and learning in order to guarantee academic achievement for all students. The job of the principal is rapidly transforming from one that merely consists of encouraging the efforts of teachers to one that also includes leading teachers to generate measurable outcomes.

The Department of Education (DepEd) is putting an expanded and intensified focus on empowering school heads and putting an emphasis on school-based administration. This significant trend of practice in the ongoing reform of education is aimed at enhancing the quality of educational services provided by the government as well as schools that are either public or private. There is now a rise in the number of public high schools in the Division of Apayao that are classified as annex schools. These schools are distinguished by the fact that they are situated in locations that are distinct from their mother schools. Principals from the mother schools are the ones in charge of managing and supervising activities at these annexes. As a result of the division's need for more school heads in these annexes, aspirational educators now have the possibility to become principals within the division. One of the qualifications to qualify for a post as a school head is to pass the National Qualifying Examination for School Heads (NQESH), but there are additional requirements pertaining to the management, administration, and leadership of a school.

For Fall (2015) SBM is more is more on an enabling mechanism for other goals to materialize. He clearly states in an earlier work that educational restructuring such as SBM needs to dovetail with the goals of systemic reform. He formulated a “framework of twelve dimensions of educational restructuring that are grouped into three subsets: central, enabling, and supporting variables. Learner outcomes, curriculum, instruction, and assessment make up the central variables, labeled as such because they have a powerful direct effect on student learning. Enabling variables, also closely related to instruction, consist of learning environment, technology, school-community relations, and time. Supporting variables, those further removed from the classroom, consist governance, teacher leadership, personnel structures and working relationships.”

According to Goden et al. (2016), policy makers and implementers need to be reminded of the findings that "simply increasing resource allocations will not increase the equity or improve the quality of education in the absence of instructional reforms" (World Bank, 2007, page 1). For an SBM to be successful, all of the education sector's stakeholders need to participate in its implementation in a way that is both effective and relevant. Furthermore, all areas of educational management need to be in sync with activities linked to decentralization.

As to the context-specify of SBM – because its implementation is dynamic, its practices cannot be boxed in a template to be followed by school heads. Every country and every locality that practices SBM is well aware of its context-based implementation.

Interestingly, while SBM was integrated in implementing the Third Elementary Education Project and the Secondary Education Development and Improvement Program in 2001 until 2005, SBM carried out as a national policy in the Philippines in 2006 as the lynchpin of the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA).

Recognizing the need to improve quality education, the DepEd engages in a continuous reform movement. In 2006, formulated the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda or (BESRA), a package of policy reforms that seek to create a basic education sector capable of attaining the country's Education for All (EFA) objectives by the year 2015. The DepEd had it developed in consultation with various stakeholder groups and consultants. The National Education for All Committee (NEC) of the DepEd enumerated the four major objectives of BESRA:

1. Universal Coverage of Out-of-School Youths and Adults in the Provision of Basic Learning Needs: All persons beyond school-age, regardless of their levels of schooling should acquire the essential competence to be considered functionally literate in their native tongue, in Filipino or in English.
2. Universal School Participation and Elimination of Dropouts and Repetition in First Three Grades: All children aged six should enter school ready to learn and prepared to achieve the required competencies from Grades 1 to 3 instruction.
3. Universal Completion of the Full Cycle of Basic Education Schooling with Satisfactory Achievement Levels by All at Every Grade or Year: All children aged six to eleven should be on track to completing elementary schooling with satisfactory achievement levels at every grade and all children aged twelve to fifteen should be on track to completing secondary schooling with satisfactory achievement levels at every year.
4. Total Community Commitment to Attainment of Basic Education Competencies for all: Every community should mobilize all its social, political, cultural, and economic resources and capabilities to support the universal attainment of basic education competencies in Filipino and English." (p. 2-3, NEC, DepEd, 2006).

The supervision and enhancement of various instructional and pedagogical methods constitutes an essential component of educational administration, which is also known as instructional leadership. The Department of Education (DepEd) is the major organization in charge of ensuring that the Philippines' educational system maintains a high standard.

Statement of the Problem

This research undertaking is designed to evaluate the school heads' performance on the use of school-based management as a tool towards educational leadership.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the school heads in terms of the following variables?
 - a. personal (age, sex, civil status)
 - b. professional (highest educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service in DepEd, length of service as school head, number of teachers supervised, student population, number of trainings attended for the last two years)
2. What is the school-based management (SBM) performance of the school heads in terms of the following variables?
 - a. leadership and governance
 - b. curriculum and instruction
 - c. accountability and continuous improvement
 - d. management of resources?
3. What is the degree of receptiveness of the teachers and stakeholders to the interventions introduced by their school heads?
4. To what extent have the school interventions contributed to school development as perceived by the school heads and teachers?
5. Is there a relationship between the school head's School-Based Management performance and select variables?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive-correlational design to answer the research questions in which it determined the school-based management performance, the degree of receptiveness of teachers and stakeholders to the interventions introduced by their school heads, the extent to which the school interventions have contributed to school improvement, and teachers' performance.

The study was conducted in the Division of Apayao, particularly at the Upper Apayao. District. Apayao is a province located in the northern part of Luzon. It is almost equally mountainous/hilly (Upper Apayao) and flat (Lower Apayao) with intermittent patches of valleys and plateaus. The focus of the study are secondary schools located in the Upper Apayao which these schools are geographically far from each other.

The respondents of the study were the secondary school heads and permanent secondary teachers teaching in all schools of Upper Apayao. Initially, 17 full-fledged secondary school heads and designated Teachers-In-Charge were covered in the study, however, due to the pandemic restrictions imposed by the barangays where five of the schools are located, 12 secondary schools were only covered in the study.

For the teacher samples, only the permanent teachers who have been under the school head for at least two years and who were available and willing at the time of school visit were included as samples in the study, Initially, 128 teacher samples were required. However, due to the pandemic restrictions one hundred ten teachers were access shown below. In addition, three teachers mentioned by the school heads as those who have improved in their teaching performance were informally interviewed to determine the specific forms of assistance extended by the school head and how these interventions gradually improved their teaching performance.

The questionnaire for the school heads is composed of Part I gathered the personal and school-related profile of the school heads. Part II elicited the assessment of the school heads pertaining to his/her school performance using the SBM tool.

The interview protocol consisted of six questions to elicit responses that described the challenges the school has encountered in the delivery of instruction under the new normal; how these were resolved; what professional development activities/actions and assistance for teachers were provided; what ways have the school benefitted from the instructional leadership; and how the school heads and the stakeholders carry out the varied dimensions before and during the new normal mode of education.

The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using the identified statistical treatment. SPSS version 26 was used to process the data.

Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data which included These included frequency counts, percentage and standard deviations and weighted means.

School Performance (SBM Tool)

Arbitrary Scale

1-Level I

2-Level II

3-Level III

Descriptive Equivalent

Developing

Maturing

Advanced

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the relationship between the set of independent variables and dependent variables. The hypotheses of the study were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1: Personal Profile of the School Heads

Category	Frequency (n =12)	Percent
Age		
40 – 45	2	16.7
46 – 50	5	41.7
51 – 55	3	25.0
56 – 60	2	16.7
Mean = 47.3 SD = 3.6		
Sex		
Male	7	58.3
Female	5	41.7
Civil Status		
Single	1	8.3
Married	10	83.3
Widowed	1	8.3

Table 1 shows the personal profile of school heads. It reveals that 5 or 41.7 percent of the respondents have ages 46-50 years while 3 or 25 percent have ages 51-55 years. Moreover, both the ages 40-45 and 56-60 have 2 or 16.7 percent, respectively. The school heads have mean age of 47.3 years. As regards sex, it shows that 7 or 58.3 percent of the respondents are male while 5 or 41.7 percent are female. This finding shows that there are more male school heads than females. In terms of the civil status, 10 or 83.3 percent are married, meanwhile single and widowed are both 1 or 8.3 percent, respectively.

Table 2: Professional Profile of the School Heads

	Frequency (n =12)	Percent
Highest Educational Attainment		
BS with Master’s Unit	1	8.3
Master’s Degree Holder	3	25.0
Master’s Degree with PhD Units	8	66.7
Plantilla Position		
Teacher III	7	58.3
Head Teacher I	2	16.7
Head Teacher III	1	8.3
Principal I	1	8.3
Principal III	1	8.3
Length of Service in DepEd		
15 – 19	4	33.3
20 – 24	5	41.7
25 & longer	3	25.0
Mean= 22. 4 yrs SD = 4.3 yrs		
Length of Service as School Head		

1 – 5	4	33.3
6 – 10	3	25.0
11 & longer	5	41.7
Mean= 10.2 yrs SD = 2.1 yrs		
Number of Teachers Supervised		
1 – 5	2	16.7
6 – 10	2	16.7
11 – 15	5	41.7
16 & more	3	25.0
Mean =12 SD = 3.5		
Student Population		
100 – 150	2	16.7
151 – 200	2	16.7
201 – 250	2	16.7
251 & more	6	50.0
Number of Trainings Attended (last 2 years)		
1 – 5	5	41.7
6 – 10	5	41.7
11 & more	2	16.7
Mean = 6 SD = 2.3		

Table 2 presents the professional profile of the respondents. With respect to the respondents' educational attainment, 8 or 66.7 percent are master's degree holder with PhD units followed by 3 or 25 percent who are master's degree holder and 1 or 8.3 percent has BS with master's degree unit. On the other hand, the respondents' plantilla position shows that majority are Teacher III which 7 or 58.3 percent followed by Head Teacher I (2 or 16.7 %), Head Teacher III (1 or 8.3%), Principal I (1or 8.3%) and principal III (1 or 8.3 %). It can be noted that majority of the school heads are holding plantilla positions that are not for administration and are not passers of assessments for such purpose. This trend is attributed to the fact that there are few qualifiers who could be appointed, thus, school head designation to those with Teacher III positions.

Also, as to the respondents' length of service in the DepEd, there were 5 or 41.7 percent who rendered 20-24 years while 4 or 33.3 have rendered 15-19 years. There are 3 or 25 percent who were in the service for 25 and longer years. Overall, these school heads had been in the service for an average of 10.2 years. As for the length of service of the respondents as school head, it reveals that 5 or 41.7 percent belongs to 11 and longer years of service, 4 or 33.3 percent are 1-5 years and 3 or 25 percent are 6-10 years. The findings indicate that majority of the school heads have a reasonable experience to be able to serve as school heads.

With respect to the respondents' number of teachers supervised, 5 or 41.7 percent have 11-15 teachers and 3 or 25 percent have 16 and more teachers. Moreover, 2 or 16.7 percent have 1-5 and 6-20, respectively. At an average, the school heads supervise 12 teachers in their respective school assignments. Such number indicates that the school heads are managing quite a small number of teachers in their school, which is considered manageable. In terms of student population, 251 and more is the highest population which is equivalent to 6 or 50 percent of the respondents, followed

by 201-250, 151-200, 100-150 populations which are all equivalent to 2 or 16.7 percent, respectively. These numbers would show that the school heads are managing a large number of students in their school which will consequently mean also that they have more stakeholders to deal with.

In terms of the respondents' number of trainings attended for the last two years, 5 or 41.7 percent attended 1-5 and 6-10, respectively. There were 2 or 16.7 percent out of the 12 school heads who have attended 11 or more trainings for the past two years. This figure yields an average of 6 trainings attended. Such number of trainings may have helped them in performing their managerial roles and responsibilities as school heads. As attested in the study of Alonzo (2020), trainings and seminars would always help teachers and faculty equipped themselves in order to give the best deliverables to their students. It is therefore imperative that teachers would always update themselves through seminar- workshops that would succor them, to be efficient and effective teachers of the youth.

Table 3: School-Based Management Performance of the School Heads in terms of Leadership and Governance

Indicators	Descriptive Value	Frequency (n = 12)	Percent
1. In place is a development (e.g, SIP) developed collaboratively by the stakeholders of the community.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	11	91.7
	Advanced	1	8.3
2. The development plan is regularly reviewed by the community to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	Developing	2	16.7
	Maturing	10	83.3
	Advanced	0	0
3. The school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	12	100
	Advanced	0	0
4. A leadership network facilitates communication between and among schools and community leaders for informed decision-making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	9	75
	Advanced	2	16.7
5. A long term program is in operation that addresses the training and development needs of the school and community leader.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	6	50
	Advanced	6	50

Table 3 presents the school-based management performance of the school heads in terms of leadership and governance. It reveals that out of the 12 school heads, the majority if not all have maturing level in the four indicators of leadership and governance. This finding is attributed to the fact that the school heads have already served for about 10 years. Such experience coupled with trainings provided has equipped them with the needed skills to govern their own schools.

All the school heads claimed that their school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders. School heads have shown great leadership abilities as well as effective governance procedures, which have benefited the general operation and development of

their schools. They have demonstrated a clear vision as well as the capacity to inspire and drive their staff, students, and the rest of the school community. They are proficient in steering their school to organize with a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders. It means that they understand the impact of a well-defined structure and established work arrangements that encourage collaborative leadership and governance on the school's attainment of its vision, mission and goals.

Furthermore, these leaders have built a collaborative and inclusive culture, cultivating good ties with teachers, parents, and other stakeholders. Under the new normal, teachers remarked that their school heads were challenged but tried so hard to cope the demands of the situation. They stated,

“Our school principal takes the initiative in implementing the challenging task of modular instruction, particularly in managing the printing, distribution, and collection of modules.”

“The effective governance of our school principal has fostered cooperation and support from barangay officials, PTA, and other community members to facilitate the distribution and collection of modules.”

On this finding, Pragss (2018), argued that ideally, the school is organized around a clear structure and work arrangements that foster shared leadership and governance while clearly clarifying the roles and duties of the stakeholders. The school administration has put in place a well-defined organizational framework that maintains a logical hierarchy and encourages collaboration among all members of the school community. The roles and responsibilities of each stakeholder, including the principal, teachers, staff, parents, and students, are clearly defined and articulated.

On this finding, an OECD (2003) report identifies key elements of effective school governance, leadership, and management, including the need for clear roles and responsibilities, accountability and transparency, the use of data and evidence-based decision-making, and the involvement of stakeholders in the education process. It also emphasizes the importance of building capacity among school leaders and ensuring that they have the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively manage schools.

About 92 percent of the school heads acknowledge that there is in place is a development plan developed collaboratively by the stakeholders of the community. There is a sense of ownership among the stakeholders when they are involved in developing the school improvement plan. These stakeholders are more likely to support the school activities if they are part of crafting the development plan. Along with this argument, Cambridge International (2014) describes the school development cycle, which includes the creation of a School Development Plan, as a critical process for setting goals, implementing actions, monitoring progress, collecting evidence, and evaluating outcomes. One teacher commented,

“Our school principal plays a vital role in school planning. We have transitioned from extensive brainstorming and idea testing to a structured planning process. Task forces have been assigned to carry out specific responsibilities within their jurisdiction.”

On the importance of collaboration in school governance, the website Giving Compass (2022) highlights the importance of various stakeholders, including families, schools, and communities, in supporting the goals of the education system. It emphasizes the need for collaboration among stakeholders to create the conditions for students to thrive. It suggests the role of each stakeholder group in supporting student success and suggests strategies for effective collaboration among them. School heads and teachers mentioned that such processes were followed to ensure continual delivery of instruction:

“The school has conducted an orientation session for parents to inform them of the responsibility in the education of their children.”

“The school has designated focal point person in every barangay as a medium to orient parents in the conduct of modular learning.”

“A learning hub in each barangay was set up so that parents and learners are made aware of the updates in the conduct of new normal education.”

“With the mobility restricted within the community, I talked to the barangay captain and other councilors and the police officers to help distribute and retrieve learning modules in their sitio political jurisdiction.”

“All barangay officials proposed the barangay gymnasium as distribution and retrieval centers of learning modules where parents could claim and submit completed modules.”

The school head’s ability to network with community leaders and among themselves school leaders is apparent when 75 percent claimed that a leadership network facilitates communication between and among schools and community leaders for informed decision-making and solving of school-community wide learning problems. On this note, Cambridge International (2014) underscored that leadership of school development demands a complex set of skills and qualities. This will be a mixture of expertise and abilities best found in a team or a network of leaders. It argued that each individual leader will bring their own set of skills and attributes to the group. These will combine with those of others to make a powerful whole. Discovering, inspiring, motivating and developing this network of leaders of learning is one of the most demanding but rewarding roles of a school principal.

Interestingly, 6 or 50 percent of the school heads have proficient performance along the existence of an operational plan to address the training and development needs of the school and community leaders. Capacity building is essential in the school organization for all the stakeholders to carry out the duties and responsibilities set in the school improvement plan.

Alongside with this need to plan for the new normal of education, teachers commented:

“Our school principal plays a vital role in school planning. We have transitioned from extensive brainstorming and idea testing to a structured planning process. Task forces have been assigned to carry out specific responsibilities within their jurisdiction.”

“Our school principal organizes weekly brainstorming sessions with our team. Our willingness to be open-minded greatly assists us in adapting to the challenges of the new normal, while brainstorming enables us to generate solutions that ease our anxieties.”

According to Sa’ud (2019) schools that do not have the capacity or quite clear capability would have trouble in making various efforts for continuous improvement effectively. Thus, for the school improvement plan to achieve the school’s vision, mission, and goals, there is a need for all stakeholders to be equipped with the needed competencies for them to actively participate.

The findings suggest that the school heads engage stakeholders in decision-making of whatever progress that the school is planning. Furthermore, it implies that customary role of the school head has therefore changed under SBM as decision-making is shared among community stakeholders and it requires school heads to exercise leadership that fully promotes their full participation. In a study, Bandur et al. (2021) reported that devolving authority to school level decision-makers has resulted in increased participation and commitment, which led to improved teaching–learning environment. The finding suggests the significance of sustainable empowerment on the part of school councils as well as leadership in-service training to school principals for an effective implementation of SBM policy and practices in developing countries. In another study, Risi et al. (2020) proved that SBM can facilitate practitioners in terms of school committee involvement in strategic decision making in varied ways, like setting of school missions, vision, objectives; repair of buildings; governing of fund; and curriculum development.

In a research, Supriadi et al. (2021) affirmed that good school governance facilitates the participation of teachers and stakeholders in the decision-making process. Furthermore, the good school governance improves the decision-making quality through the empowerment of teachers, the delegation of authority, and the encouragement of shared decision-making.

Table 4: School-Based Management performance of the school heads in terms of Curriculum and Instruction

Indicators	Level	Frequency (n = 12)	Percentage
1. The curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	7	58.3
	Advanced	5	41.7
2. The implemented curriculum is localized to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	6	50
	Advanced	6	50
	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	9	75

3. A representative group of school and community stakeholders develop the methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving.	Advanced	3	25
4. The learning system are regularly and collaboratively monitored by the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	6	50
	Advanced	5	41.7
5. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	5	41.7
	Advanced	6	50
6. School heads and learning facilitators (teachers, HLMF, administrators, community members) nurture values and home learning environments that are protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the VMG.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	9	75
	Advanced	2	16.7
7. Methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped with essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume responsibility and accountability for their own learning.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	5	41.7
	Advanced	7	58.3

As gleaned from Table 4, the school heads' SBM performance in terms of curriculum and instruction is **maturing** in most of the indicators while the others have **advanced** performance. This is particularly noted in the indicators 1, 2, and 3. It shows that programs and localized curriculum were developed in the new normal which were fully implemented and monitored by the school. Although hard up in the initial months of the implementation of the new normal of education, the school heads strove hard to cope with the demands of the circumstances. School heads declared their difficulty:

“It's challenging because we're not used to it. We are still getting used to the new standard manner of instruction. The creation of learning modules necessitates procedures in which teachers initially lacked proficiency.”

“Although our instructors initially had difficulty, they were eventually inspired to design learning modules as a result of networking with other teachers at the school and other institutions in the district.”

Also, learning materials and approaches to reinforce strengths and address learning gaps were developed. There are indicators, though, in which one out of the 12 school heads performed at a beginning level. This is attributed to the location of the school and the availability of the school supplies and facilities feedback teaching and learning. There are schools too far from the places with good internet connection, sources of print materials, and distribution of learning materials. Strategies used varied, as attested by the school heads and teachers:

“At times, because of the limited printers, distribution of learning modules is delayed. As such, the retrieval is also affected.”

“In areas with access to Internet, we provide some learners the soft copy of the learning modules to reduce the number of copies to be reproduced, thus lessening the burden of additional funds in the reproduction.”

“We are lucky because generous stakeholders give voluntary material donations in support of the school. They give bond paper, printer ink, and even printer as they are aware of our struggles.”

“Our barangay and police officials are so helpful in the new normal as they offer the barangay vehicle and patrol cars to deliver learning modules.”

“Remote areas are reached through barangay volunteers traveling in motorbikes.”

Mechanisms for effective assessment and feedback were also implemented and were strictly monitored by the school management through the strong support of the community stakeholders. Owing to the restrictions imposed during the pandemic, school heads and teachers find difficulty doing valid and reliable assessment of learning because learning could not be monitored well. Allegations of parents' failure to monitor or assist their children and some doing the students' assignments, were reported by some teachers:

“How can I accurately evaluate the students' success if they did not complete the exercises themselves? And some parents have high expectations for their kids' academic performance.”

“Some activities in the modules that were submitted weren't fully or adequately answered as parents could not adequately monitor their children's learning because they have no or limited education to explain the lessons.”

“I noted that the parents were the ones providing the responses on behalf of their kids, as some of the responses do not correspond to what the kids have been through.”

According to Well (2021) school heads need also place a premium on using data to influence decision-making and improve instruction. They ensure that teachers have access to relevant student performance data, allowing them to identify areas for growth and adapt education based on the requirements of individual students. A culture of assessment and evaluation is promoted by effective school leaders, who encourage teachers to use formative and summative exams to monitor student development and adapt teaching tactics accordingly.

Overall, the results reveal that continuing drive for raising standards in education with an emphasis on collaboration and partnership with others for the benefit of all was manifested that lead to excellent school improvements. It is admirable that the curriculum considers the developmental

requirements of various types of students in the school environment. This inclusive approach to education is crucial for ensuring that all students, regardless of learning preferences, backgrounds, or abilities, have access to high-quality instruction.

Educators and administrators who are knowledgeable about SBM can successfully adopt this strategy in their schools and guarantee that all views are heard during the decision-making process. Improvements in student achievements as well as increased ownership and dedication to the success of the school may result from this, as revealed in the **maturing level** by 58.3 percent of the respondents. Educators argue that effective principals encourage the continuous development of teaching procedures. They give teachers with excellent assistance and professional development opportunities, allowing them to improve their instructional abilities and tactics. These leaders foster an environment of innovation and creativity in the classroom by encouraging teachers to use a variety of teaching methods, technology, and resources.

On this need, school heads used varied strategies. Some explained theirs:

“At first, it was difficult for teachers to write a whole lesson in their learning modules. But offering advice and support gradually raises their spirits and confidence that they could produce a quality learning module.”

“During the lockdown, I managed to keep a team together regardless of whether teachers were at work or at home. When formulating plans or thinking through issues and challenges the school encounters, instructors are accustomed to working in teams and interacting with one another.”

“Teachers were able to reduce their stress levels by working in teams to manage their job and personal lives. These teams assisted one another to manage workloads during the pandemic, ensuring the school had uninterrupted instruction.”

This claim is asserted by one teacher-respondent who said,

“My principal shows a strong dedication to curriculum and instruction. She places a premium on the creation of high-quality curriculum, assist teachers in improving their instructional techniques, and foster a culture of continual improvement. She establishes a learning environment that promotes student accomplishment and engagement by encouraging creativity, collaboration, and the effective use of data. Her commitment to curriculum and instruction guarantees that students receive a well-rounded and relevant education that will prepare them for future success.”

In attaining this goal, mustering the support of all stakeholders is essential. Bandur (2008) mentioned that SBM is a strategy that can be used to improve the efficacy of schools by bolstering the dedication of faculty members and fostering a sense of ownership among students. It has the ability to raise the standard of educational provision.

On the other hand, an enhanced level of community involvement would be beneficial to every single institution (Meador, 2019). According to the findings of numerous studies, schools that have larger support systems tend to fare better than those that do not have such help. The support for the school comes from a wide variety of sources, both inside and outside the institution. An effective school leader will utilize a number of different techniques in order to win over the support of the entire community for the school. This situation is affirmed by teachers:

“The curriculum and instruction are strictly monitored by my school head. He watches classrooms on a regular basis, provides constructive criticism to teachers, and offers advice on how to improve teaching procedures. He promotes teacher collaboration by fostering the exchange of best practices and the creation of educational materials and tools.”

“The school heads sought the help of barangay leaders and the police force to help ensure the continuity of learning among the students. Through them and other volunteers and focal point persons, the distribution and retrieval of learning modules are coordinated well.”

For the school heads and teachers, when a curriculum is localized, it is created to match the needs, interests, and values of the neighborhood's students and community. This indicates that the curriculum's subjects are pertinent to the experiences and environment of the students. As a result, students are better able to relate to the subjects covered and comprehend how to use what they have learned in their everyday lives. It is believed in indicator 6 that by adapting the implemented curriculum to their local context, students can practice critical thinking as they identify and address issues in their neighborhoods.

Teachers confirmed with their own experiences in the preparation of localized printed modules to meet the needs of their learners. They stated:

“Initially, we relied on the modules published by the national education department. Later, the learning modules were localized and contextualized as required to make learning relatable to the experiences of the students.”

“Localizing the instructional materials was easy because we have been doing that in our daily classes. Only this time, we have to transform and illustrate it in printed form.”

As students begin to understand how they may benefit their community, this familiarity also fosters their confidence and self-esteem. It fosters a sense of accountability and responsibility for their part in the neighborhood as residents. Localizing the applied curriculum enables students to get a deeper appreciation for and understanding of their own heritage. Furthermore, it helps them become more involved and effective community members by preparing them for dealing with real-life issues.

Home learning environment (HLE) is also essential in enhanced curriculum implementation. In fact, it is an important predictor of differences in children's academic and social development

(Lehrl et al, 2020). The necessity of providing a setting in the family that encourages children to have a passion for learning and behave in a constructive manner is emphasized in this article. They went on to say that in order to encourage children's growth in an appropriate manner, collaboration between parents and educators should bridge the two learning contexts of home and preschool. The scientific evidence on the impact of collaborative activities on children's development is, however, mixed, and this topic needs further research.

In instances where some students could not submit learning outputs, the school heads encouraged teachers to conduct home visits, in coordination with the barangay leaders and police officers. As related by the teachers, they have conducted the following strategies:

“We often conduct home visits to students who could not submit learning modules. There we realize that they are out of town. For some students, they ask their siblings to answer the modules.”

“Those with access to Internet are text messages to follow up their submission.”

“We tell parents to assist their children. However, they are preoccupied with their farming activities, which is their priority.”

“Some children are helpless because they admitted their parents did not reach a higher level of education for them to be of help.”

Indicator 6 also accounts that school heads and learning facilitators, such as teachers, HLMF, administrators, and community members, play an important role in instilling values and creating home learning settings that are safe for all children. These adults may establish safe and supportive environments for children to succeed intellectually and socially by continuously displaying actions that fit with the Vision-Mission-Goals. One of the primary advantages of this strategy is that it fosters a culture of inclusion and respect. Students are more inclined to mimic positive behaviors and attitudes modeled by instructors and other adults. This can assist to prevent bullying, discrimination, and other unpleasant behaviors that can have a significant impact on children's mental and emotional health.

However, as earlier presented, some problems are encountered with home learning environment. Parents and more knowledgeable siblings, at times, are the ones answering the learning modules. When parents fail to monitor the completion of the modules by their children, students submit incompletely answered modules. All these affect the acquisition of the most essential learning outcomes of the subjects.

On this need, Reyes (2016) that the importance of developing values and creating home learning settings that protect all children stems from the fact that they provide the groundwork for lifelong success. We can assist ensure that children are resilient, self-sufficient, and capable of reaching their full potential by providing them with the tools, skills, and values they need to handle the difficulties of the world around them.

Table 5: School-Based Management performance of the school heads in terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Indicators	Levels	Frequency (n = 12)	Percentage
1. Roles and responsibilities of accountable persons and collective bodies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	8	66.7
	Advanced	4	33.3
2. Achievement of goals is recognized based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system; gaps are addressed through appropriate action.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	8	66.7
	Advanced	4	33.3
3.The accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanism are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	8	66.7
	Advanced	3	25
4. Accountability, assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	6	50
	Advanced	5	41.7
5. Participatory assessment of performance is done regularly with the community. Assessment results and lessons learned served as basis for feedback, technical assistance, recognition and plan adjustment.	Developing	2	16.7
	Maturing	6	50
	Advanced	4	33.3

Table 5 presents the SBM performance of the school heads in terms of accountability and continuous improvement. As revealed in the table, the accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanism are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community, assessed **maturing level** by 66.7 percent. It means that the school heads are aware of their responsibility to establish an accountability system that is community-owned, continuously improved, and responsive to the evolving needs and demands of the community. Such recognition ensures that schools are held accountable for their actions and strive for continuous improvement in their educational practices. Moreover, both the school head and community stakeholders play a key role and take accountability in the delivery of needed services, assessed with a level of maturing (66.7 percent). This indicator underscores the need for the school heads to increase community involvement through delegation of responsibilities which are regularly monitored and evaluated.

In the new normal education, school heads feel the weight of their accountability as the parents and learners and other stakeholders expect them to effect an education that still ensures the attainment of the desired education of learners.

School heads averred:

“Doubly-taxing is our responsibility during the pandemic as we are challenged to produce learning modules. With limited resources, we make do of what we have to meet the expectations of the stakeholders.”

“We are lucky to have local supporters who are willing to help us provide a continuing education. The barangay officials and police men and women are ever willing to bring us to the remote homes of students, just to deliver modules.”

“Teachers, though pressured, did their best to produce learning modules to comply the needs of providing a continuing education of their learners.”

“We coordinated our activities with the other stakeholders so that a collaborative action can be tapped to keep the momentum of learning continue.”

To develop an environment that supports continuous improvement, encourages risk-taking, and stimulates innovation, school leadership, and educational administration must collaborate. By doing this, they can guarantee the effective implementation of SBM which will lead to better student results and a more effective and efficient educational system (Thormn (2019). Particularly, shared, and participatory processes are used in determining the roles, and responsibilities of stakeholders in managing and supporting the new normal education. School and community stakeholders developed a performance assessment that serves as the basis for improving the monitoring and evaluation of technical assistance and refining plans.

One teacher-respondent stated,

“The principal actively includes teachers and staff in the process of continual development.

She promotes a collaborative and reflective culture in which educators participate in professional learning communities, shares best practices, and receives ongoing professional

development. She assists her team in finding opportunities for growth and implementing new

techniques to improve teaching and student outcomes by hosting regular discussions and

feedback sessions.”

Consequently, effective school heads also involve parents, students, and other stakeholders in the accountability and improvement process. They create strong channels of communication and collaboration by incorporating parents in decision-making processes and soliciting their feedback

on school policies and procedures. They actively listen to suggestions and concerns and respond appropriately, fostering a collaborative and supportive school climate (Braggs, 2019).

When accountability, evaluation criteria, feedback mechanisms, information collecting, and validation methodologies and procedures are designed collectively, it is probable that a wide range of stakeholders and viewpoints have been considered. This enhances the possibility that any possible prejudices or blind spots have been acknowledged and addressed, and that the program is culturally acceptable and relevant. This indicator obtained **maturing** level of rating (50 percent).

In the new normal, school heads and teachers acknowledged that the feedbacks of students and parents at the initial implementation were very useful to improve the delivery of instruction. They shared their varied experiences:

“Distribution of learning modules at the beginning was chaotic. Upon noticing this difficulty, there was a need to strategize. Seeking the help of barangay leaders was resorted to, and it works.”

“Designating focal persons were identified in every barangay was one helpful mode of easing the burden of distribution and retrieval of modules. This was a response to the delayed issuance of learning modules.”

“Students complained about the context and situations found in the learning modules published by the national department. This necessitated the urgency of localizing and contextualizing the modules by the teachers. That resulted to easier understanding of the lessons.”

Research findings in various countries demonstrate that through the implementation of SBM, school stakeholders and participants have been empowered in decision-making, leading to create high levels of parental and community participation (Bandur, 2008). Finding point out that there have been school improvements and student achievements resulting from the implementation of SBM. By promoting experimentation, creativity, and risk-taking, school leaders build a culture of continuous improvement. They instill a growth mentality in instructors, staff, and students, emphasizing the importance of learning from mistakes and using them to progress. Effective school heads foster a welcoming and inclusive climate in which mistakes are viewed as opportunities for growth and achievement.

Table 6: School-Based Management performance of the school heads in terms of Management of Resources

Indicators	Descriptive Value	Frequency (n = 12)	Percentage
1. Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	7	58.3
	Advanced	4	33.3
2. A regular dialogue for planning and resource programming, that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage stakeholders and support implementation of community education plans.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	7	58.3
	Advanced	4	33.3
3. In place is a community-developed resource management system that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	7	58.3
	Advanced	5	41.6
4. Regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.	Developing	1	8.3
	Maturing	9	75
	Advanced	2	16.7
5. There is a system that manages the network and linkages which strengthen and sustain partnerships for improving resource management.	Developing	0	0
	Maturing	7	58.3
	Advanced	5	41.7

Undoubtedly, the area of management resources is the weakest aspect of SBM among the school heads under the new normal. All items receive a rating of 58.3 percent, described as proficient.

The majority of the school heads have **maturing** SBM performance in terms of management of resources (Table 6). Specifically, regular resource inventories are conducted jointly by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as the foundation for resource mobilization and allocation; an ongoing, accessible, and inclusive dialogue for planning and resource programming engages stakeholders continuously and supports the implementation of community education plans; and a resource management system created by the community is in place and encourages stakeholders to act in the right ways.

The finding means that a collaborative and inclusive approach to resource management exists in schools. The involvement of learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders, as well as the emphasis on regular dialogue, monitoring and partnerships, highlights a commitment to effective resource allocations, utilization, and accountability.

In the new normal, resources are scarce as schools need funds to produce learning modules to be distributed to the learners. School heads were concerned of the limited funds available, as claimed by them.

“What can you do with the 500 pesos per capita in the production of learning modules? Each student has to be given modules for all the subjects in the grade. This amount is not really enough for the entire lessons.”

“My teachers are lucky as they are given material assistance by generous individuals in the community. Even without asking, bond paper and printer ink are donated by relatives, friends or former students.”

“Our police officers in town volunteered to deliver the learning modules and retrieve the same when they go on patrol in the barangays where the students are located.”

“Module distribution and retrieval is facilitated with the focal point persons and the assistance of the barangay leaders. This is done at no cost to the school.”

These mechanisms reflect the ability of the school heads to muster all available resources to facilitate the implementation of the education in the normal. The fact that the barangay people offer their services to the school, without cost, manifests the school's winning the trust of the people. It also reflects the people's trust on how the school manage their resources. Also, the school's financial statements and other inventory records are disclosed to stakeholders including list of donations with acceptance and partnership established.

On the other hand, actively involving community people aids in the discovery of new resources that may be helpful in the implementation of educational initiatives. This can entail getting funding from benefactors or using the knowledge of community members and organizations.

As affirmed by a teacher-respondent,

“The school leader places a premium on transparency and accountability in resource management. He keeps correct financial records and documentation while complying to set standards and rules. Effective principals promote ethical practices and ensure that financial resources are utilized for their intended objectives, minimizing waste and mismanagement.”

As advocated by Borne (2017) the key to successfully implementing community education programs in a school with school-based management is a regular discourse that is open, inclusive, and ongoing. Stakeholders identify the resources needed and potential difficulties with the implementation of educational programs through this discourse. Additionally, it guarantees that each person's requirements are met and offers ongoing participation to modify programs and find new opportunities.

Table 17: Receptiveness of the Teachers and Stakeholders to the Interventions Introduced in their Schools

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Not receptive	-	-	-	-
Somewhat receptive	4	33.3	2	1.8
Receptive	7	58.3	32	29.1
Very receptive	1	8.3	47	42.7

Table 17 presents the receptiveness to the interventions introduced by the school heads in their schools, as assessed by the school heads and teachers that have been introduced in their schools. In terms of school heads, the majority of school heads, 58.3% (7 out of 12), were classified as "Receptive" to the interventions. Additionally, 8.3% (1 out of 12) were categorized as "Very receptive," implying a high level of support and enthusiasm for the introduced interventions. None of them was categorized as "Not receptive" to the interventions.

On the other hand, among the teachers, the data suggest a more varied response. The largest group of teachers, 42.7% (47 out of 110), fell under the category of "Very receptive," while the majority, 29.1% (32 out of 110), were classified as "Receptive. The findings indicate high level of acceptance and endorsement of the interventions introduced by their school heads. A small proportion, 1.8% (2 out of 110), were considered "Somewhat receptive" to the interventions."

Literature on change management and educational interventions supports the significance of receptiveness in implementing successful changes in educational settings. When stakeholders, such as school heads and teachers, are open and receptive to interventions, it can foster a positive environment for innovation and improvement. Research indicates that receptiveness is associated with a higher likelihood of adopting new practices, implementing interventions effectively, and achieving desired outcomes (Brown, 2014; Hallinger, 2015).

The receptiveness of teachers and stakeholders to School-Based Management (SBM) interventions presented in their schools varies, but there are various aspects that contribute to their overall receptiveness. For starters, effective communication and engagement techniques are critical. Teachers and stakeholders are more likely to be responsive when they are fully informed about the goal, benefits, and implementation strategies of SBM interventions. Clear and open communication aids in the resolution of any problems or misunderstandings, and it allows for active engagement and collaboration in the process. Involving teachers and stakeholders in the decision-making and planning stages of SBM interventions increases ownership and buy-in. Teachers and stakeholders become more invested in the success of interventions when they believe their voices are heard and their opinion is respected. Their active involvement in developing the treatments boosts their receptivity and commitment to the changes that are being implemented.

One teacher-respondent propounded,

“Adequate assistance and resources are critical in earning the acceptance of teachers and

stakeholders. Implementing SBM interventions frequently necessitates additional training, capacity-building, and resource allocation. Teachers are more likely to embrace changes when they obtain the required training and support to comprehend and

effectively implement the interventions. Similarly, when stakeholders realize that the resources needed to guarantee successful implementation are being supplied, their receptivity grows.”

According to Prods (2019) positive results and evidence of impact can have a substantial impact on receptiveness. When teachers and stakeholders see the beneficial consequences of SBM initiatives, such as improved student achievements, increased parental involvement, or improved school atmosphere, it strengthens their faith in the approach's efficacy. Sharing success stories, data, and evidence-based research can assist teachers and stakeholders gain confidence and openness.

Cultivating a culture of constant development and learning is critical. Based on feedback and evaluation, SBM treatments may require revisions and enhancements. When teachers and stakeholders are involved in the monitoring and evaluation of interventions, and their input is welcomed and used, it promotes a feeling of communal responsibility and openness to continuous improvement. A culture that values innovation, introspection, and adaptability fosters an openness to novel treatments and supports openness to change.

Table 18: Extent to which the School Interventions Have Contributed to School Development

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Number of teachers doing action researches	1.92	Little	2.09	Little
2. Teachers' development of learning modules	3.00	Much	2.77	Much
3. Teachers' training/INSET on specialized learning areas.	2.58	Much	2.85	Much
4. LAC sessions addressing learning needs.	3.25	Much	3.07	Much
5. Evaluation of learning outcomes through Class observation.	3.17	Much	3.15	Much
6. Technical assistance in teaching areas	2.92	Much	2.96	Much
7. Quality of teaching in school.	3.00	Much	3.03	Much
8. Enhancement of learners' achievement	2.92	Much	3.07	Much
9. Improvement of school image to the community	2.75	Much	3.20	Much
Overall Weighted Mean	2.83	Much	2.90	Much

Legend:

1.00 – 1.75 *Not at all*

1.76 – 2.50 *Little*

2.51 – 3.25 *Much*

3.26 – 4.00 *Very much*

Quality of teaching emerged as a second important indicator of school improvement, as shown by the means of 3.00 (school heads), and 3.03 (teachers) indicating Much. The importance of the quality of teaching in schools as a key indicator of school development and improvement cannot be over-emphasized. High-quality teaching positively impacts student achievement, equity, engagement, and teacher-student relationships. It necessitates ongoing professional development and a commitment to continuous improvement to ensure that students receive the best possible education.

By prioritizing and supporting the quality of teaching, schools can create an environment conducive to student success and overall school improvement. Academic achievement and student outcomes can benefit from school initiatives. Improved student performance can be achieved by effective instructional methods, targeted interventions for challenging students, and the use of evidence-based teaching methodologies. Interventions that meet students' unique needs, such as remedial programs, differentiated education, or enrichment activities, can help to enhance academic performance and overall school performance.

As shared by teacher-respondents, school interventions are useful:

“School interventions have the potential to improve the quality of teaching and learning. Teachers’ instructional practices can be improved via professional development efforts, mentoring programs, and collaborative learning opportunities.”

“Interventions contribute to educator professional growth by providing teachers with the required knowledge, skills, and support, resulting in improved teaching effectiveness and student engagement.”

Interestingly, in the study of Alieto (2021) school interventions can help to create a healthy and welcoming school climate. Positive conduct, conflict resolution, and social-emotional learning interventions all contribute to a safe, supportive, and respectful learning environment. These interventions aid in the creation of a sense of belonging, the reduction of disciplinary concerns, and the improvement of student well-being. A positive school climate promotes student motivation, involvement, and overall happiness with the school.

Effective school interventions can help with school management and governance. Implementing interventions that strengthen school leadership, administrative processes, and data-driven decision-making can lead to more efficient and effective school management. Interventions that improve school governance structures, stimulate stakeholder participation, and establish transparent accountability procedures all work together.

In the interviews, both school heads and teachers recognized that the quality of teaching in schools is a critical indicator of school development and improvement. They argued that high-quality teaching has a profound impact on student learning outcomes, engagement, and overall school success, as supported by their high rating on enhancement of learners' achievement (2.92 and 3.07, respectively). Numerous studies have consistently shown a strong positive relationship between the quality of teaching and student achievement (Darling-Hammond, 2017; Rockoff et al., 2020; Rivkin et al., 2018). Moreover, emphasizing the quality of teaching in schools encourages ongoing professional development and a commitment to continuous improvement. Teachers need opportunities for professional learning, collaboration, and feedback to enhance their instructional practices and keep up with evolving educational research and best practices (Wei et al., 2020; Opfer et al., 2021). Recent literature emphasizes the importance of high-quality professional development programs that are job-embedded, evidence-based, and provide sustained support for teachers' growth (Timperley et al., 2017; Desimone et al., 2021).

Moreover, school heads and teachers agree that the quality of teaching in schools is a vital indicator of school development and improvement. Teachers are at the center of the educational process, directly accountable for enabling student learning and growth. Student involvement, motivation, and academic accomplishment are all directly affected by the quality of teaching. Clear instruction, diversified training, and active learning tactics all improve deeper understanding and long-term retention of knowledge. Recognizing the importance of teaching quality, school leaders and teachers place a premium on ongoing professional development and seek out chances to improve their instructional skills and knowledge.

Teacher-respondents reinforced this view:

“Teaching quality is highly related to student accomplishment and academic growth.”

“Effective teachers are well-versed in their subject matter, instructional practices, and assessment methodologies. They are capable of identifying and meeting individual student

needs, providing timely and constructive feedback, and implementing appropriate educational interventions.”

“Skilled teachers can modify their instruction to match their students' different learning styles, talents, and backgrounds, ensuring that every student has equitable access to quality education.”

The teachers' giving high rating (3.20, as contrasted to the school heads' rating of 2.75) on improvement of school image to the community signifies the importance of the school in building a positive impression among the community stakeholders. In the course of interviews with the school heads and teachers, they alleged that building a good school image is essential in school-based management as it contributes to various aspects of school development and community engagement, especially in generating funds in support of school projects and activities. By focusing on building and maintaining a positive reputation, schools can enhance their overall development, student outcomes, and community relationships.

Recent literature underscores the importance of building a good school image in school-based management. A good school image helps foster strong relationships with the local community. When a school is perceived positively, community members are more likely to support school initiatives, participate in school events, and engage in collaborative partnerships (Epstein et al., 2019; Sudzina & Kilcher, 2019). Recent literature emphasizes the importance of community involvement in promoting student success and overall school improvement (Bryk et al., 2015; Sheldon & Epstein, 2019). A positive school image enhances community engagement and creates a sense of shared responsibility for education.

In addition, a positive school image contributes to the overall school culture and climate. When a school is perceived positively, it creates a welcoming and supportive environment for students, teachers, and staff (Wang & Degol, 2018; Wang et al., 2020). Recent research indicates that a positive school climate has a direct impact on student well-being, academic engagement, and learning outcomes (Wang et al., 2019). A good school image enhances the sense of belonging and contributes to a positive and conducive learning environment.

Interestingly, teachers' development of learning modules emerged as a positive contributor to school improvement, as manifested in the 3.00 rating of the school heads and 2.77 by the teachers. Both indicate Much contribution. Interviews revealed that at the time of the pandemic, early difficulties in the preparation of modules was strongly felt by the teachers. However, with the professional and technical assistance of the school heads, they gradually coped with the need of producing, distributing, and retrieving learning modules.

In the interviews, both school heads and teachers recognized that teachers' development of learning modules gained significant importance in school-based management, as learning must continue during the Covid-19 pandemic. As learning modules are structured instructional materials that provide guidance, resources, and activities for students to engage in remote or blended learning environments, learners through the assistance of parents and siblings can learn the most essential learning competency which is desired in all the subjects.

Literature abounds to underscore the need for learning modules in crisis situations. The pandemic necessitated a rapid transition to remote learning, and teachers had to adapt their teaching methods to suit online platforms. Developing learning modules allowed teachers to design and deliver coherent and well-organized instructional materials that could be easily accessed and understood by students in a virtual environment (Ferdig et al., 2020; Hodges et al., 2020).

In addition, learning modules have facilitated the adaptation to remote learning, allowed for individualization and differentiation, provided continual assessment and feedback, and promoted teacher collaboration and professional development. By investing in the development of learning modules, schools can support effective remote instruction, enhance student engagement, and ensure equitable access to quality education during challenging times (Gewerc et al., 2020; Lekwa et al., 2021).

Table 20: Relationship Between School Based Management Performance of the School Heads and Select Variables

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Probability	Statistical Decision
SBM Performance and			
Age	0.296	0.350	Not significant
Sex	-0.736	0.006	Reject Ho at 1% level
Civil Status	-0.035	0.915	Not significant
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.418	0.177	Not significant
Plantilla Position	-0.015	0.962	Not significant
Length of Service as DepEd Employee	0.384	0.217	Not significant
Length of Service as School Head	0.432	0.161	Not significant
Number of Teacher Supervised	0.331	0.293	Not significant
Student Population	0.399	0.199	Not significant
Number of Training/Seminars Attended	0.325	0.303	Not significant

The association between School -Based Management performance of the school heads and select variables is presented in Table 20. It can be seen that school-based management performance of the school heads are not significantly correlated to select variables such as age, civil status, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service as DepEd employee, length of service as school head, number of teacher supervised, student population, and number of training/seminars attended as indicated in the probability values which are all greater than 0.05. It means that performance along the indicators of SBM are not dependent or are not affected by such variables.

Sex is the only variable that has a significant relationship to School-Based Management performance of the school heads as indicated by an r-value of -0.736 ($p = 0.006$). As the categories of sex were coded 0 for Males and 1 for Females, the finding means that male school heads have higher levels of SBM performance than their counterparts. SBM performance is affected or is influenced by sex in favor of the male. According to Mulford and Silins (2016), a comprehensive review of research on educational leadership highlights the relationship between leadership and school outcomes. It discusses various aspects of leadership, including the influence of the school head's sex, and its impact on school-based management performance. In addition, while the study of Koller and Schnabel (2013) focuses on student performance, it provides insights into gender differences and the impact of interest on performance. Understanding the influence of gender and

interest can indirectly contribute to understanding the impact of the school head's sex on school-based management performance, as it highlights the potential impact of gender-related factors on educational outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS

In the light of the findings, the study concludes that school heads have demonstrated proficiency in school-based management, particularly in leadership and governance, within the context of the "new normal." They have shown a high level of competence across various indicators of instructional leadership, especially in providing teaching performance feedback and creating a conducive learning environment. Consequently, teachers have been receptive to the interventions introduced by the school heads, resulting in improved evaluation of learning outcomes, addressing learning needs through LAC sessions, enhancing the quality of teaching, and achieving better academic success, thus enhancing the school's reputation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study findings and conclusions derived in the study, the following are suggested:

1. Although the school head manifested favorable levels of SBM performance, there is a need for DepEd officials to continuously provide professional development programs and training opportunities for school heads to enhance their leadership skills, particularly in areas related to instructional leadership, communication, decision-making, and governance. This will ensure that they are equipped with the necessary competencies to effectively lead and manage their schools.
2. To ensure collaborative partnership of stakeholders, school heads should actively involve the community in decision-making processes and develop a shared vision for the school. Efforts should be made to foster partnerships with parents, local organizations, and stakeholders to create a supportive and collaborative environment that aligns with the school's objectives.
3. School heads should tap the varied stakeholders (LGU, alumni, PTCA, and other groups) in generating fund support to ensure that schools have adequate financial resources, personnel, and training to support school-based management initiatives effectively. Investing in educational materials, infrastructure, technology, and continuous professional development for teachers and school heads is crucial for achieving positive school outcomes.
4. As the teachers and other stakeholders are significant partners in achieving the vision, mission, and goals of the school, the school heads need to create a school culture that promotes cooperation, creativity, and continuous improvement. It is essential for them to encourage open communication, teamwork, and a sense of shared responsibility among teachers, students, and staff. Likewise, fostering an inclusive and supportive environment that values diversity and encourages innovation should be one of the priority considerations.

5. Adapting SBM to local context should be always practiced. There is urgency of recognizing the unique needs and challenges of the local context and adapt school-based management approaches accordingly. Taking into account the cultural, social, and economic factors that may influence the effectiveness of instructional leadership and tailor strategies to address specific local requirements is one step to win the support of the stakeholders and create a good image for the school.
6. As data-driven decision-making is desired in SBM, school heads should continuously emphasize the importance of using data to inform decision-making processes. On this regard, DepEd should provide school heads with tools and training to collect, analyze, and utilize data effectively. Division of Apayao officials should encourage evidence-based practices and use data to identify areas of improvement, track progress, and make informed decisions.
7. Because there are gender disparities in SBM performance, DepEd should take steps to address it by providing equal opportunities for professional development and leadership growth for both male and female school heads. There is a need to promote gender equity and create an inclusive environment that values and supports the contributions of all school leaders.
8. Since most of the school heads assigned in the Upper District of the Division of Apayao are Teacher-in-Charge, with a Teacher III plantilla only, the concerned authorities of the Division should encourage these school heads to take the National Qualifying Examination for School Head so that they would have more chances of being qualified for promotion to principal positions.
9. A parallel study may be conducted considering other profile variables and education metrics in a bigger sample size and wider geographical region for greater generalizability of study findings.

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